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Cognitive Activities and Social Experiences of School Paper Advisers in Public Elementary Schools in Santa Cruz District, Division of Laguna: Basis for Capability Training in Campus Journalism for Teacher-Advisers

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Abstract.

Writing is a form of communication that allows students to put their feelings and ideas on paper, organize their knowledge and beliefs into convincing arguments, and convey meaning through well-constructed text. The study aimed to determine the cognitive activities and social experiences of the school paper advisers in all public elementary schools in the Santa Cruz District, Division of Laguna. The researcher also wished to use the study's results as a basis for developing capability training in campus journalism for teacher-coaches and advisers. The study also explored the relationships between cognitive activities, the social experiences of the school paper advisers, and the level of performance in campus journalism. The study's sample consisted of 150 school paper advisers from public elementary schools in Santa Cruz, Laguna. A self-made questionnaire was used to assess the cognitive activities and social experiences of the school paper advisers. The data collected from their responses to the questionnaires were analyzed using weighted means in statistical software. To see if there are any significant relationships between SPA's cognitive activities and social experiences, Pearson *r* tests were computed. Based on the findings of the study presented, the following conclusions were drawn: Most of the school paper advisers in all public elementary schools in Santa Cruz, Laguna, were found to "always" engage in different cognitive activities to enhance their skills in teaching campus journalism. Most of them preferred reading to creating their own blogs online. The advisers' social experiences were expansive and can be used to motivate teaching campus journalism. The results also indicated that the advisers needed a social life to improve their performance as school paper advisers. The district's performance was "poor," indicating it needs intensive training and workshops to improve. The results also indicated that the district has not received any awards in the national contest for the past three years. The results also revealed that the top five contest categories in the district were Collaborative Desktop Publishing, Script Writing and Radio Broadcasting, Photojournalism, Feature Writing, and Science News Writing. Finally, it was concluded that, in general, the cognitive activities of the school paper advisers were not related to the school's and the district's performance levels. Cognitive activities might enhance their personal well-being and capacity, but not directly at the level of campus journalism performance. As with the advisers' social experiences, the school's performance was not directly affected. Positive social experiences in school and community increase one's self-esteem and social well-being, but not directly in campus journalism.